

FACTORS AFFECTING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL STATE OF AN ATHLETE**Dilnoza I. Yarasheva**Asia international university of
department of physical culture

Email: yarashevadilnozaismoilqizi@oxu.uz

Annotation: The psychological state of an athlete is one of the most important factors determining his effectiveness in training and competitions. Training loads, competition pressure, social environment and personal factors have a strong impact on the mental stability of an athlete. This article discusses the main internal and external factors affecting the psychological state of an athlete, their importance in sports activities and methods for ensuring stable mental preparation.

Keywords: psychological state, stress, motivation, athlete, mental preparation, external factors, internal factors.

Login

Along with high physical fitness, sports activities require strong psychological stability from the athlete. The results of an athlete in training and especially during the competition largely depend on his mental preparation. Because during the competition, the athlete faces many stress factors - pressure from opponents, referee decisions, the audience factor, time constraints and high responsibility. In such conditions, the athlete's ability to concentrate, overcome excitement and anxiety, control his emotions and make quick and clear decisions directly determine his final result.

The factors that shape the psychological state are complex and multifaceted, and they are internal (personal) and Internal factors include the athlete's motivation, self-confidence, character, temperament, stress tolerance, experience, and emotional stability. External factors include supportive or pressured conditions in the sports environment, relationships with coaches and teammates, level of competition, family environment, and media influence.

Therefore, in the field of sports psychology, great attention is paid to the formation of not only the physical, but also the mental preparation of the athlete. After all, a psychologically unstable athlete, even with a high level of physical preparation, cannot fully demonstrate his potential in the competition. On the contrary, mental stability, stress resistance and self-confidence are the decisive factors for the athlete's success in the competition.

Main part**Internal (personal) factors**

- Motivation - an athlete's participation in training and competition should be goal-oriented. High motivation strengthens the athlete's morale.
- Self-confidence - a correct assessment of one's capabilities and self-confidence reduce stress.
- Emotional stability - performance increases when an athlete can manage excitement, fear, and anxiety.
- Psychophysiological characteristics - temperament, character and personal qualities - shape the mental state of an athlete.
- Experience - athletes who have trained and competed many times become more mentally stable.

External factors

- Relationship with the coach - A supportive, motivating, and trustworthy coach has a positive impact on the athlete's morale.
- Team environment - positive relationships between team members reduce stress, while a negative environment does the opposite.
- Competition conditions - audience pressure, opponent strength, and the level of competition - affect an athlete's mental stability.
- Support from family and loved ones gives the athlete a sense of psychological confidence and security.
- Media and social media - pressure or criticism towards an athlete can directly change their mentality.

Methods for strengthening the psychological preparation of an athlete

- Stress reduction through autogenic training and meditation.
- Psychological training (motivation, self-confidence building).
- Visualization and self-motivation techniques.
- Pre-competition psychological modeling exercises (e.g., imagining an opponent, visualizing victory).
- Regular work with a coach and sports psychologist.

Conclusion

The psychological state of an athlete is one of the most important factors determining his performance in training and competitions. Although physical fitness is the foundation of sports results, without mental stability these capabilities cannot be fully manifested. Therefore, a deep analysis of the internal and external factors that shape the psychological state and their scientific management occupy a special place in the methodology of sports training.

Internal factors - the athlete's motivation, self-confidence, experience, character and stress tolerance - determine his psychological strength. If an athlete sets clear goals for himself and confidently strives to achieve them, he will be able to overcome psychological pressure during the competition. External factors - such as the relationship with the coach and team, the competition environment, family and social support - directly affect the athlete's internal psychological state. If they are positive, they motivate the athlete, and if they are negative, they increase stress and negatively affect the results.

In practical terms, regular psychological training, stress management exercises, motivational interviews, visualization and autogenic training are of great importance to strengthen the psychological readiness of an athlete. Also, cooperation between the coach and the sports psychologist plays an important role in maintaining the mental stability of athletes.

Therefore, the formation and stabilization of the athlete's psychological state is not only a personal effort, but also a complex process that must be carried out with the participation of the coach, team, family and sports psychologist. Only such a comprehensive approach will help the athlete fully realize his physical potential and achieve consistently high results in competitions.

References

1. Dilnoza, Y. (2023). SUB'YEKTIV VA SPORT.
2. Dilnoza, Y. (2024). SOG'LOMLASHTIRUVCHI MASHG'ULOTLARNING TURLARI VA SAMARADORLIGI.
3. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). SPORTS PEDAGOGY BASED ON PSYCHOMOTOR AND DEVELOPMENT THEORIES. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(12), 26–41. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-05>

4. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). PHYSIOLOGICAL REACTIONS TO INTERNAL LOAD STUDY. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(12), 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-07>
5. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). SPORTS, CULTURE AND SOCIETY. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 152–163. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-17>
6. Yarasheva, D. (2024). IN HANDBALL GYMS: SAFE PHYSICAL EXERCISES AND INJURY PREVENTION. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 23–32. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/30639>
7. .Yarasheva, D. (2024). USE OF HANDBALL INDUSTRY AND TECHNOLOGY. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 9–15. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/30575>
8. Yarasheva, D. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF ENDURANCE IN HANDBALL. International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology, 4(3), 73–77. Retrieved from <https://internationalbulletins.com/intjour/index.php/ibet/article/view/1406>